

Knowledge, attitude, and practice towards volunteerism: a perspective from Sultan Idris Education University

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ABSTRACT

Volunteering requires a high level of commitment to community development, especially from young people. The first study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitude and practices of university students of education regarding volunteering and the second study, analysing the differences in students' knowledge regarding interest in volunteering. The survey method using Google form was distributed among the students of volunteer course semester 2 2022/2023 at Sultan Idris Education University. A total of 459 respondents provided the feedback. Overall, students' knowledge about the volunteer course was excellent. Their attitudes towards volunteering activities tend to undertake activities related to their interests in terms of the types of volunteers available. Encouraging things in volunteering practice shows that students keep learning things related to volunteering, keep looking for opportunities to help others, and influence others to do it together. The analysis of students' knowledge related to volunteering among students by interest showed that there was a significant difference in the mean of students' knowledge by interest, where respondents' interest in volunteering for the community was much higher than in other volunteering activities. Further studies should be conducted to better understand volunteerism among high school students who are now immersed in technology.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The strength of nation-building lies within a society that values togetherness, including among university students. This can be seen through the reform movements led by students, such as social justice and others. These movements arise because today's students are inheriting a world filled with significant challenges, ranging from environmental destruction to armed conflicts. To ensure that students can overcome each challenge, they must possess leadership skills that incorporate universal values such as integrity, compassion, justice, and altruism to guide them in making ethical decisions [1].

The issue of social justice that still persists today should be addressed with the involvement of students, whether at the secondary or higher education level. Students in higher education have a significant voice in society. This is because university students, as agents of societal and national change, will face the real world after graduation. This reality requires students to equip themselves with diverse knowledge and skills. Efficiency in self-management is a key aspect for advancing a nation toward well-being. Through inclusive learning, professional development can help students fulfill their social responsibilities [2].

This professional development is also contributed by the involvement of students in volunteer activities, which leads to psychological well-being [3].

The report for the Asia-Europe Foundation (ASEF), emphasised that universities should engage their students in volunteer work [4]. Volunteering on campus provides an experience that is not possible in the lecture hall. Moreover, volunteering allows students to learn about social issues in the area. An unpaid work is a great limitation for individuals because today's world is heavily dependent on money [5]. The economic factors show that volunteering cannot overcome the social factor, which is empathy for the environment. Volunteering should become a habit in all walks of life, as it involves people freely giving their time to help others or groups. Volunteers are not only able to solve problems, but can also attract the attention of individuals who are concerned about the well-being of the community as a whole [6].

A curriculum designed in line with the development of young adults can prepare a society with a high quality of life [7]. To strengthen the value of professional development through the aspect of volunteering, understanding the approach that can assess how much students are exposed to the concept of volunteering is a key factor. This is because, ultimately, it helps students consistently take the right actions. Therefore, volunteering as active learning in educational institutions can help solve problems in the student learning process. This can be achieved with an academic environment that enhances and supports positive collaboration through discussion and critical thinking [8].

To encourage the development of students who play a role in improving the quality of life in society, emphasis on the process of socialization is an effective method. This is because students will emulate this learning process to better understand their responsibilities outside the classroom. This can be practically influenced as explanations related to knowledge, skills, and attitudes in developing students' critical thinking directly impact the learning process [9]. Educational components that emphasize the theoretical aspects of socialization can fundamentally lead to critical knowledge, positive attitudes, and significant practices towards a harmonious society. Direct socialization can enliven students with various learning elements such as motivation, experience, and behavior. The practice of socialization is relevant in motivating the cultivation of social relationships and community life [10].

Previous studies have shown that knowledge about volunteering influences a person's motivation, which in turn is influenced by a caring attitude. Therefore, to understand student volunteering, more attention should be paid to their knowledge and attitudes. Volunteers who function as problem-solving groups have specific functions related to improving well-being through immediate assistance. Individuals' awareness and attitudes towards volunteering should be increased, as is the case in European countries included in the Global Peace Index because the contribution of volunteers can lead to greater peace, community, and accountability [11]. There are numerous benefits for individuals who volunteer. For students, volunteering locally not only fills up their free time, but also has a positive and lasting impact on their personal development.

The people who volunteer have a higher level of performance because they have a productive attitude towards their employers and always display a good personality to improve the company's image [12]. An individual who spend a lot of time or volunteer frequently, as included in a résumé, are hired faster than individuals who excel but are inactive in community activities [13]. Six aspects increase ease a person's potential when participating in volunteer activities, namely values, understanding, social, career, protection, and even self-improvement. These six aspects prepare individuals to build social capital, which is important for the country as it can promote initiative and motivation for human welfare [14].

The knowledge, attitudes, and practices of volunteers have a significant impact on a community. Through their volunteer activities, they can facilitate the creation of awareness about certain issues. This is similar to what is happening in northern Ethiopia. The volunteering can raise the villagers' awareness and improve knowledge about the implementation of government programs, such as the spread of tuberculosis, which has been identified as a major health problem in Ethiopia. The role of volunteers can give people in northern Ethiopia the confidence to work together to prevent the disease from harming themselves and the community. As a result, the health of the population has improved by 30% [15].

In Papua New Guinea, volunteers play a role in promoting clean births by using contraception. This is because hygiene during the birth process is still low leading to an increase in disease transmission. The practice of hand washing before cutting the umbilical cord is considered unnecessary and time-consuming, as it is not used by mothers or families to ensure that the birth process environment is clean for a long time. This has led the Ministry of Health to encourage volunteers to help improve knowledge, attitudes, and practices related to hygiene during childbirth. Community awareness was raised by the volunteers when birth kits were distributed to mothers, which were considered 'handbags' [16].

The volunteer engagement should be increased in every area, especially in village areas; the area of health. This is because villagers should be introduced to health care due to relatively distant access to the hospital and because of the high costs. The volunteering can directly improve cooperative relationships among the residents if many people are committed to working together. The most important factor is that health knowledge is high, which in turn shapes attitudes and practices to help the village community.

The results of the study show that this form of volunteering can improve one's skills in interaction and empathy in Khlong Luang community, Pathumthani [17].

To improve the practice of volunteering in the community, the management of an organisation should incorporate volunteering through appropriate training and education strategies. Volunteerism can shape productive attitudes among employees. Organisations can also improve the quality of services provided to their employees when volunteering activities are carried out because they not only convey a caring attitude but can also improve the image of individual in the organisation, which in turn has an impact on the organization [18]. This is because employees are part of the society in which they work and live with. A job satisfaction includes volunteering activities.

Volunteerism has always been prevalent among college students, particularly in teaching and planning activities. However, educational institutions can enhance student engagement by utilizing student financial aid reform. One way to achieve this is by integrating community services and encouraging student participation. It is crucial to increase financial support for student activities and maximize its utilization to foster the development of leadership skills among college students [19]. Participation in these voluntary activities demonstrates the impact of behaviour on student practice, whether in the form of study or off-campus life.

The participation of young people in volunteering activities in higher education has revealed the existence of identity. However, the impact of identity is not as prominent unless it is linked to personal fulfillment. Students are more likely to be involved in volunteering when their contributions are acknowledged and valued by others. The influence of identity on volunteering engagement becomes more significant when they are entrusted with responsibilities such as being a group leader, community leader, or mentor. This is because it can shape both their identity and their role as a volunteer. The role of identity is indeed crucial for volunteers, especially students, as it is an important source of life experiences while growing up [20]. Off-campus, students need to actively plan and carry out a variety of activities that benefit themselves and others. This type of activity is crucial to Khlong Luang society because it promotes civic engagement [21].

Volunteering encourages students to become more socially engaged, involved in the community, and more invested in their education. As students, they have the opportunity to make a valuable contribution to strengthening democracy, driving social change, and fostering personal and professional growth through community service. By participating in extracurricular activities, such as civic engagement programs, students can actively shape the political landscape and even become active members of the government.

Volatility has a direct impact through transactional and relational properties within psychological relationship theory. Both of these properties are grounded in economic partnerships and enduring social ties. Volunteering is a matter that is very much linked to migration, whether through money, energy, and ideas, which in turn strengthen relationships. This psychological relationship is to prevent the occurrence of threats in society. As a result, students will be prepared with a stable emotion during the study period and equipped with positive attitude constantly. This will enable them to engage themselves and the university more in the society [22].

Volunteering activities are fun things. This is because such activities provide opportunities to travel and learn about the culture. A pleasure is when there is a learning process that is not bound to a system. It can give students satisfaction to learn outside of the lecture hall. It also trains students' ability to adapt quickly to the situation so that they can bring out their talent. High self-confidence during study or after graduation can help students deal more competently with others [23]. The results of the study show that personality development is the most important aspect achieved through active participation in volunteering activities. This will encourage them to continue to engage with high morale.

The study at Dhofar University showed a low rate of volunteering activities. It also showed that sports and cultural organisations were the main beneficiaries of students' "volunteer activities", as well as local agencies. The study found that altruistic motivations were most frequently cited as reasons for volunteering, namely religious beliefs. Promoting national belonging, a desire to fill free time, and gaining work experience were also important motivating factors. Students were clear that they wanted to make a difference through their volunteering, and some preferred to select activities that allow them to have a greater impact. Student volunteers reported many positive impacts on their personal development, skills, and employability [24]. Students cited lack of time due to their studies as the biggest barrier to volunteering.

The mentor-mentee program among university students also significant. Mentors among students who are not from a university setting can cultivate new things. Undergraduate students can mentor students from schools near the university through a mentor-mentee program [25]. A mentor between student and student can improve the quality of education in both universities and schools. With different mentoring backgrounds, mentors can also deepen the culture for future career continuity. Therefore, the volunteer work

of colleges should be planned as well as possible in terms of management to implementation, so as not to cause problems for both parties.

Voluntary activities should be more widespread, especially among students, to produce competent students who can quickly adapt to their environment. Behavioural change occurs not only through books but also through volunteer experiences. The learning transformation will be able to accelerate the process of connecting current problems with solutions through critical thinking [26]. Meanwhile, a critical thinking is observed when an individual receives and stores new knowledge, while interrelating and applying such information to address unfamiliar situations. It is the ability of individuals to interpret, evaluate and manipulate previous experiences, in order to confront present life challenges [27]. This is because volunteers need to take immediate action to raise awareness about something. Studying university volunteers is vital for several reasons. Firstly, understanding the motivations and experiences of these volunteers can offer valuable insights into what drives individuals to engage in volunteer activities during their academic years. Research suggests that volunteering among university students can contribute to personal development, social integration, and academic success. By investigating the underlying reasons for their involvement, such as altruism, social responsibility, or career advancement, researchers can tailor volunteer programs to better meet the needs and interests of students. This, in turn, fosters a culture of service and civic engagement within the university community [28].

Furthermore, studying university volunteers provides an opportunity to explore the impact of volunteering on various aspects of student life, such as academic performance, mental health, and career development. Research has shown that students who engage in volunteer activities may experience enhanced self-esteem, improved interpersonal skills, and a greater sense of purpose. These factors positively influence their overall well-being and academic outcomes [29]. An understanding these effects can inform the development of support services and interventions aimed at promoting student success.

With sufficient information such as fieldwork training, communication approaches, and leadership, it can help students evaluate various aspects of volunteer work. This can assist students in engaging in volunteer activities that require direct involvement. As a result, it can help address the imbalances that exist in society. The findings of this study can be used by students involved in volunteering to prepare themselves for the challenges of volunteering while also motivating themselves to continue contributing. Additionally, examining the patterns of volunteerism among university students can provide valuable data for policymakers, educators, and community organizations seeking to address societal challenges and promote social change. By identifying demographic characteristics, participation rates, and preferred volunteer activities among students, researchers can help stakeholders design more effective strategies for recruiting and retaining volunteers, targeting underserved populations, and addressing pressing community needs [30].

2. METHOD

2.1. Research design

A quantitative approach was used to achieve the purpose of this study. Quantitative research was conducted to discuss social facts related to the study of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of students in Sultan Idris Education University Volunteer Course. In this study, the survey was considered most appropriate for gathering information about volunteers in the context of Malaysian undergraduates. The data were collected online via Google Form platform. The invitation to participate was made through a lecturer in the WhatsApp group.

2.2. Ethical approval

The Human Ethics Board of Sultan Idris Education University had approved our research protocol, procedures, information sheets, and informed consent form (ref. No. 2021-0382-01). Respondents who agreed to the survey were instructed to voluntarily click the “Continue” button and fill out a self-administered questionnaire. The subjects of the survey consisted of students in the voluntary course of the second semester of 2022/2023. Since the training is a university course, the respondents were from various faculties. Considering the number of students enrolling in the volunteer course was 1400 using the 1% significance level, thus, the number of participants was 450. The dispensing period of the questionnaire lasted 2 weeks from January 3 to January 17, 2023. A total of 459 responses were received. The demographic statistics are shown in Table 1.

2.3. Data collection tool

The yield format is a data collection tool for this study, and there were two sections. The first section was the demographic information of the respondents constituting gender, religion, age, teacher, and the tendency of volunteer activities. The second section describes the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of volunteering. Knowledge-related questions in the second section through volunteer functions inventory

(VFI) [14]. Five scales were tested at level, there are: i) strongly disagree; ii) disagree; iii) not sure; iv) agree; and v) strongly agree. There were 13 question elements comprising the aspects of values, understanding, social, career, and improvement. The setting and practice questions about students' attitudes towards voluntary services [24]. The set consisted of 5 question elements while the exercise consisted of 3 elements.

Table 1. Demographics of respondents

Respondents		Frequency (n) percent (%)	Frequency (n) percent (%)
Gender	Male	118	25.7
	Female	341	74.3
Religion	Islam	371	80.8
	Buddha	10	2.2
	Hindu	16	3.5
Age	Christian	62	13.5
	20 years	16	3.5
	21 years	57	12.4
	22 years	269	58.6
	23 years	71	15.5
Faculty	24 years	46	10.0
	Faculty of Language and Communication	97	21.2
	Faculty of Music and Performing Arts	16	3.5
	Faculty of Management and Economics	3	0.7
	Faculty of Human Development	105	22.9
	Faculty of Human Sciences	129	28.1
	Faculty of Computer Arts and Creative Industries	39	8.5
	Faculty of Science and Mathematics	39	8.5
	Faculty of Sports Science and Coaching	19	4.1
	Technical and Vocational Faculty	12	2.6
Tendency of interest	School-based	56	12.2
	Hospital-based	12	2.6
	Animal care	37	8.1
	Environment	121	26.4
	Elder Care homes and welfare homes	66	14.4
	Institutional organisations (examples: synagogues, museums, stadiums, libraries)	44	9.6
	Community (examples: housing, aboriginal, rural)	109	23.7
Individual	14	3.1	

2.4. Statistical analysis

In this study, the data collected were analysed using SPSS version 26. The descriptive analysis focused on the frequency and percentage, and a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine the differences between selected groups. Statistical significance levels were set to $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Demographics

Table 1 shows the demographics of the respondents. Female respondents outnumbered male respondents (74.3%) (25.7%). For religion, most respondents were Muslims (80.8%), followed by Christians (13.5%) and Buddhists (2.2%). Most respondents were 22 years old (58.6%), and only 3.5% of respondents were 20 years old. 28.1% of the respondents studied at the Faculty of Human Sciences, followed by those who studied at the Faculty of Human Development (22.9%), and only 0.7% of those studied at the Faculty of Management and Economics. Regarding the tendency of interest in voluntary activities, the highest interest was in environmental activities (26.4%) followed by a trend of community interest in housing, indigenous peoples, and rural areas (23.7%), with only 2.6% interested in hospital volunteering.

3.2. Student knowledge

Table 2 is the knowledge related to volunteerism among students at Sultan Idris Education University. A total of 88.2% of students strongly agreed that volunteering was able to connect them with others compared to only 0.2% of students who disagreed and strongly disagreed. Students' knowledge that volunteering could add new contacts showed they were the highest in agreed (89.3%) and only 0.2% of students disagreed and strongly disagreed. Knowledge in terms of volunteering can improve relationships and social skills showed students strongly agreed (86.7%) and only 0.2% of students disagreed and strongly

disagreed. Volunteering can provide benefits to the mind and body showed students also stated that they strongly agreed with the highest (80.4%) and students who disagreed and strongly disagreed with 0.4%.

Another benefit of volunteering for students is that it can help them cope with stress, anger, and anxiety, as evidenced by the fact that the majority of students strongly agreed (67.1%), followed by agreed (26.4%), and strongly disagreed (0.2%). Furthermore, 64.3 percent of students strongly agreed, 26.6 percent agreed, and only 0.4 percent strongly disagreed that volunteering activities can help with depression. This is because they can mingle with a large number of individuals through volunteer activities, and there is a multi-level communication that can help them relax. Students also discovered that volunteering activities might boost self-esteem when the results showed that the majority of students highly agreed (81.5%), followed by agreed (15%), and only 0.2% strongly disagreed. Because of this, self-confidence can be developed.

Table 2. Students' knowledge related to volunteering

Item	Percentage					Mean	SD
	SDA	D	NS	A	SA		
Connecting with others	0.2	0.2	0.7	10.7	88.2	4.87	0.412
Adding new contacts	0.2	0.2	0.9	9.4	89.3	4.87	0.409
Improve relationships and social skills	0.2	0.2	0.7	12.2	86.7	4.85	0.425
Provides benefits to the mind and body	0.4	0.4	1.7	16.6	80.8	4.77	0.540
Help to overcome stress, anger, and restlessness	0.2	1.1	5.2	26.4	67.1	4.59	0.663
Fighting depression	0.4	1.3	7.4	26.6	64.3	4.53	0.727
Increase self-confidence	0.2	0.7	2.6	15.0	81.5	4.77	0.544
Helps to stay healthy	0.2	0.4	3.9	22.4	73.0	4.68	0.592
Increase a sense of responsibility	0.2	0	0.9	14.6	84.3	4.83	0.432
Increase career potential	0.4	0.7	3.9	22.9	72.1	4.66	0.630
Teach valuable job skills	0.4	0.2	4.4	19.4	75.6	4.70	0.604
Gain work experience	0.4	0.2	4.1	20.3	74.9	4.69	0.602
Give joy and satisfaction in life	0.2	0.2	2.8	20.3	76.5	4.73	0.544

Mean classification: Low (1.00-2.32), simple (2.33-3.66), and high (3.67-5.00) are the average classifications. Note: SDA=Strongly disagree; D=Disagree; NS=Not sure; A=Agree; and SA=Strongly agree; SD=Standard deviation

Student involvement in volunteer work can equip them with extensive knowledge. Knowledge in volunteer work enables students to build social relationships and have a wide network through efficient management. It has been proven that involvement in volunteer work allows students to add new contacts, improve relationships and social skills, and connect with others. Student involvement through strategic management of education and training allows them to understand the actual dynamics and the relationship between learning and the real world [31]. This is because students are entering a phase of personal maturity.

3.3. Student attitudes

Five questions were examined regarding student attitudes towards volunteering in Table 3. The attitudes of students who did not consider any risk to themselves before helping others showed the highest level of agreement (48.4%), followed by students who disagreed (28.5%) and those who were unsure (23.1%). This clearly shows that students put the welfare of others above their welfare. For attitude of students who always believe in people asking for help, 58.4% of students agreed, 24.4% were unsure, and 17.2% of students disagreed with the statement. The attitude of students of not caring about their situation while volunteering showed the highest level of agreement (43.1%). However, students who disagreed were second with 40.7% and those who were unsure were only 16.1%. This shows that even among them, many are too concerned with their situation before volunteering to make sure they do not get into trouble later.

Table 3. Student attitudes related to volunteerism

Item	Percentage			Mean	SD
	ND	NS	A		
Ignore the risk before helping others	28.5	23.1	48.4	2.20	0.855
Always trust people who ask for help	17.2	24.4	58.4	2.41	0.767
Ignore self-condition when running volunteer activities	40.7	16.1	43.1	2.02	0.917
Tend to do volunteer activities related to interests	22.7	7.6	69.7	2.47	0.839
Choose a religious background in providing individual assistance	90.6	2.6	6.8	1.16	0.521

Mean classification: 1.00-2.32=low; 2.33-3.66=simple; 3.67-5.00=high; Note: ND=Disagree; NS=Not sure; A=Agree; SD=Standard deviation

Students were more likely to do interest-based volunteering. 69.7% of students agreed, 22.7% disagreed and 7.6% of students were unsure. Volunteering for interest has a great impact on themselves and the activities are done sincerely and honestly. The last students' attitude examined in this study was when choosing a person's religious background in individual assistance, the highest number of students (90.6%) disagreed with the statement. Only 6.8% of the students agreed and 2.6% of the students were unsure. This shows that students do not have racist attitudes when it comes to providing volunteer services to those in need. Overall, it was found that student attitudes towards volunteering are positive and reject racist attitudes.

A country's human capital can be developed through the nation's ability to shape the character of its citizens, including university students. Student involvement in volunteer work directly fosters a highly empathetic attitude. As a result, students are always able to help people overcome any problems, regardless of religious background. Emphasizing character education can produce individuals who always love their country. Good character involves the transfer of values from oneself to form a sense of duty and integrity in carrying out every responsibility [32]. Pure character can be transferred into volunteer work because it involves the inclination to help the community without coercion.

3.4. Student's practices

Table 4 shows students' practice in volunteering at Sultan Idris Education University, with 89.5% of students who said yes saying that they always find ways to help others, even if they cannot help themselves. Only 8.3% were unsure and 2.2% answered negative. When asked if they always practise the characteristics of volunteering in life, 85.6% of students answered yes. 11.8% of students were unsure, and only 2.6% did not practise it. Students always learn things related to volunteering in their lives. 90.4% said yes, followed by students who were unsure about practising it (7.4%) and not practising it (2.2%). When asked how students encourage others to volunteer, 89.5% of students answered yes, 8.7% were unsure, and only 1.7% of students answered the negative. This proves that overall, students have always done volunteer work in their lives. This practice is excellent because it makes the student unselfish and able to live in a community.

Table 4. Practices of students in terms of volunteering

Item	Percentage (%)		
	Yes	No	Uncertain
Always find ways to help others	89.5	2.2	8.3
Practising the characteristics of volunteerism in life	85.6	2.6	11.8
Always learn things about volunteerism	90.4	2.2	7.4
Influence others to do it together	89.5	1.7	8.7

The transformation of higher education involves not only new-age educational methods and real-world experiences but also the stakeholders. The involvement of stakeholders in education enhances its quality. Education will involve conscious and planned efforts to create a learning environment and process so that students actively develop their potential to possess religious-spiritual strength, self-control, character, intelligence, and noble morals [33]. The involvement of stakeholders in volunteer activities carried out by students helps them remain proactive in performing charitable work, thereby improving their quality of life. This encourages students to maintain a high awareness and continually seek solutions to the challenges faced by the community and society.

3.5. Differences in students' knowledge based on their interest in volunteer activities

Table 5 is the results of Tukey test analysis showed that significant differences existed between respondents with a tendency to be interested in school volunteer activities, with $p < 0.05$ and a community with an institutional organization, $p < 0.01$. In addition, the difference in mean scores of students' knowledge by tendency of interest where respondents are interested in community volunteer activities was much higher ($M=4.87$, $SD=0.23$) than respondents interested in school ($M=4.65$, $SD=0.64$), in hospitals ($M=4.68$, $SD=0.32$), in animal care ($M=4.63$, $SD=0.53$), in environmental protection ($M=4.72$, $SD=0.38$), in nursing homes or welfare ($M=4.77$, $SD=0.36$), in institutional organisations ($M=4.57$, $SD=0.47$), and among individuals ($M=4.74$, $SD=0.43$). Table 6 is a one-sided ANOVA test of students' knowledge of volunteer activities, especially at Sultan Idris Education University, based on interest level. There was a significant difference in students' knowledge according to interest level with a value of $F(7.451)=3.321 < 0.01$.

Fundamentally, communication is an important aspect in shaping the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of volunteering, especially among the younger generation. It is the result of the socialization process conducted by formal agents, namely educational institutions. Through the socialization process, social relationships are formed through effective communication. This can be practiced by establishing connections,

awareness, and adaptation [34]. Communication should be clear in different forms and can be practised by younger generation, which includes students. This is because they have the power of energy. A form of communication such as instructions given politely, management training, and moral support, which are part of the formation of social capital, must be done in an orderly manner. Forms of communication that youth do not understand will cause them to stay away from volunteer activities [35]. An educational institution plays an important role in mobilising the practice of volunteering in higher education. This is because if the process of a policy in a higher education institution is too difficult, it is hard to achieve participation and practice for volunteering [36]. This point showing that the context of social institutions and faculty behaviours have a significant impact on students' perceptions on volunteering during college. Universities, as institutions that educate students to be good, should always be the backbone for volunteer activities [37]. This can raise awareness of the practices that students need to engage in while in college.

Table 5. Distribution of student knowledge by the level of interest

Tendency of interest	Number	Min score	Standard deviation
School-based	56	4.651	0.63618
Hospital-based	12	4.686	0.31539
Animal care	37	4.632	0.52615
Environment	121	4.718	0.38443
Old people's home or charity	66	4.773	0.36267
Institutional organisation	44	4.572	0.47285
Community	109	4.867	0.23492
Individuals	14	4.742	0.43368
Total	459	4.732	0.42216

Table 6. ANOVA test of students' knowledge according to interest tendencies

	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean squared	The value of F	Sig
Between groups	4.001	7	0.572	3.321	0.002
In group	77.624	451	0.172		
Total	81.625	458			

Through good policies, Indian government for example, with the provision of support through College Grants Commission (UGC), millions of students have gained experience in addition to intercultural learning. The developing participatory experiences in students can prepare them to accept cultural differences easily and educate them to be open-minded and care more about the community than themselves. This suggests that supporting educational institutions in volunteering provides sustainability in the community. The volunteer participation could involve a variety of social and cultural backgrounds through the collaboration of multinational institutions to boost volunteering and create good activity management by promoting a cooperative attitude [38]. The results of the study can also use the United Kingdom (UK) as an example to implement knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The volunteering in the UK, which is a government policy initiative, has engaged students to volunteer in higher education. As a younger generation, volunteering was monitored by the community to create a responsible attitude. Volunteering in the UK is the duty of both the government and the community, which leads to the activity being carried out as best as possible to create a better and safer environment [39].

Volunteer activities aim to promote civic behaviour among the younger generation. For example, the volunteering can be influenced by the motivation and benefits of the activity performed. Frequent or regular student engagement is encouraged by participation in a variety of different activities. The variety of these activities can increase motivation while providing many benefits, either directly or indirectly. Evans *et al.* [40] stated that the situation is almost similar with the students in Australia, Canada, New Zealand, the United Kingdom, and the United States.

4. CONCLUSION

Volunteering is of great benefit to the learning process and is closely related to academic achievement. Many significant benefits are received by students involved in volunteering. It not only involves high altruism but also equips students with various skills. These skills are useful throughout their lives. To achieve the goal of student volunteering, work-integrated learning must be practised. Volunteering should be based on work-integrated learning because there are needs that the community has for students, such as the expected outcomes of program implementation, the place of implementation, and the management organization. If these needs are put aside, the community cannot acquire the benefit as volunteering is supposed to have an impact on the local community and environment. The aspect of needs

should be emphasised in volunteer activities because it enhances the aspects of students' knowledge, attitude, and practices related to volunteer activities. This study on volunteering provides inclusive findings in enhancing the quality of higher education students. However, this study has limitations that can be addressed through further research. To develop a civilized society, volunteer education needs to be instilled among secondary school students because, at a young adult age, knowledge about the well-being of the people needs to be imparted as early as possible. This allows students to consistently develop character from a young age to adulthood. Therefore, volunteering that involves community service should not be overlooked in the learning process of a nation to strengthen a balanced physical and spiritual life for society.

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